

CYBERBULLYING AGAINST TRANSGENDER IN SOCIAL MEDIA: SYMBOLIC INTERACTIONISM PERSPECTIVE

Ari Wicaksono¹

¹Department of Communication Studies, UPH Graduate School, Universitas Pelita Harapan Jakarta, Plaza Semanggi, Jakarta 12930, Indonesia

ariwicak9295@gmail.com

Abstract

The transformation of social interaction between individuals into Social Networking Site (SNSs) such as Twitter and Instagram, etc., has significantly raised new phenomenon to be investigated. In Indonesia, the Cyberbullying phenomenon has emerged as recent issue in communication technology, communication and media studies. This study aims to draw the red thread of the Cyberbullying interaction process through the symbolic interactionism theoretical framework. The object of this study is Mimi Peri Rapunchelle, an Indonesian Celebrity Instagram that has been viral among Indonesian Instagram users. The pictures, video scripts and follower's comments are taken as the primary data of this research. By using descriptive-qualitative approach, the process of Cyberbullying on Instagram was started from three stages: (1) internal conflict in victim's self-identity, (2) society collective interpretation towards victim's visual identity (3) visual society response towards victim existence in Social Media reflected by visual text and emoticon.

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1. Background of Study

Cyberbullying phenomenon in the era of media convergence is described as a form of cyber crime against someone who is done through Computer Mediated Communication (CMC) technology. The presence of Social Networking Sites (SNSs) is one of the factors of bullying in cyberspace (Circello, 2013). The fundamental difference between SNSs compared to other CMC technologies lies in the account owner's personal profile, the relationship between users, and the comments or testimonies that can be seen by the public (Ahmad, 2011). Furthermore, Social Networking Sites (SNSs) are also described as a virtual community that encourages many people to interact and to communicate each other by creating identity profiles, sharing, and posting photos and captions (Waheed *et al.*, 2017). Warner describes SNSs as a form of web-based meetings and interactions that are increasingly popular to be used in order to build personal relationships / contacts, establish friendships, and develop personal relationship (Jun, 2009). Based on these description, the term SNSs refers to applications or social networking sites that are widely used today such as Facebook, Instagram, MySpace, Flickr, Youtube, Twitter and LinkedIn (Brandtzæg, 2012). The increasing of Cyberbullying trends through social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram has attracted many observers and researchers to study this phenomenon in depth (Nocentini *et al.*, 2010; Bauman and Yoon, 2014; Dolev Cohen, 2014). Research conducted by the Ditch the Labels shows that Cyberbullying

behavior is almost done on all types of social media networks. Using a research sample of 10,000 young british aged 12-20 years, as many as 17% of children claim to be victims of Cyberbullying. Specifically, 42% of children were bullied through Instagram, 37% through Facebook, 31% through Snapchat, 9% were bullied via Twitter, and the remaining 3% were bullied through the Thunbrl (Constance, 2017). In case of this study, Instagram was considered able to provide the intimidator a virtual space where it gives chance to intimidator to modify his personal identity anonymously. This anonymity gives intimidator a sense of security to carry out aggressive attacks against victim (Donegan, 2012).

In Indonesia, forms of Cyberbullying speech are easily found in almost all of social media accounts. In general, the form of cyberbullying utterances can be found on social media owned by public figure. In some sample, these public figures have many followers that they will response any kind of posting includes to comments, to like or to share. In Indonesia, Celebgram is one sample of public figures. It refers to ordinary Instagram user who has millions of followers where every photo uploaded into his/her personal account becomes trending to their followers (Krisnawati, 2016). The Indonesian celebrity Instagram account named Mimi Peri Rapuncelle being viral and quite controversial among instagram users. In the real world, name of "Mimi Peri Rapunchelle" refers to the male sex identity with the real name is Ahmad Jailani, the owner of Mimi Peri Instagram accounts. Modifications of photos made by Mimi Peri resembling women and palace fairy triggered derogatory comments of "dajjal", "sissy", "effeminate", or "madman".

Cyberbullying behavior carried out by followers of Mimi Peri is form of response towards individual in virtual space. In the perspective of George Herbert Mead, the process of communication between individuals involves symbols in the form of signs and language that can be interpreted by each individual (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015). In this study, the Symbolic Interaction process is used to describe the process of interaction between objects or victims with intimidator. To explain its analysis and conclusions of the study, this research begin by describing the elaboration of the Symbolic Interaction theoretical framework, the research methodology used, analysis of data collection and drawing conclusion.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 Symbolic Interactionism

The core of Symbolic Interactionism was first introduced by George Herbert Mead in his book entitled *Mind, Self, and Society* which was published in 1934 (Waskul, 2014). According to Korgen and White, Mead's concept of symbolic interaction emphasizes the process of community interaction in everyday life through symbolic interaction, and how community groups create a sign and meaning (Aksan *et al.*, 2009). Mead emphasizes four main conceptions in Symbolic Interaction, including: (1) humans act based on the meaning of objects they have, (2) interactions occur in certain social and cultural situations where a person's physical and social background, in a condition, is defined and categorized based on personal interpretation, (3) the emergence of meaning comes from a process of interaction between individuals and community groups, (4) the meaning is created and continuously changed through the process of interpretation and interaction between individuals (Carter and Fuller, 2015). The concept of Symbolic Interaction was then developed and split into two main school namely the Chicago School and Iowa Indiana School. Although both schools refer to Mead's concept of thinking, incase of metodological approach, the Chicago school emphasizes the use of qualitative descriptive methodology in understanding phenomenon of social interaction in society, while

the Iowa Indiana School emphasizes the positivistic approach through quantitative analysis approach (Carter and Fuller, 2015)

As one of the founders of the Chicago school, Herbert Blumer applied this theory of symbolic interaction for analysing the social phenomenon in psychology and sociology (Waskul, 2014). Both studies, psychology and sociology, have been well-known as branch of social cluster that learn about the existence of human. Herbert Blumer developed the concept of Symbolic Interaction, as taught by Mead, into three main premises, those are: (1) humans act towards something based on the meaning contained in the object (2) a meaning of symbol exists through individual interaction in a society (3) meanings are used and modified through a process of interpretation by individuals collectively (Waskul, 2014). Considering those premises, the construction of symbol meaning in a social life were constructed and interpreted by society collectively. Although this theory derived from the sociological studies, Griffin considers that both symbolic interaction theory conceptualized by Mead and Blumer has a close connection in understanding the process of interaction and communication in a community group. In this case, Griffin reviewed the Symbolic Interaction theory both in the Mead and Blumer's viewpoints by drawing tree specified premises, those are: (1) meanings constructed through social reality, (2) language is a source of meaning, (3) thinking is a process of taking the role of others (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015).

The essence of Blumer's concept of symbolic interaction theory, according to Griffin, draws the humans act towards individual based on the meaning through the symbol or gesture of an object or individual. In this case, the interpretations carried out were only individual, but also combined. This meaning is not only limited to an individual, but also the social environment. In carrying out the process of meaning, humans are influenced by stimulus on their cognition to a condition that is being faced so as to encourage the emergence of an action or response. According to Griffin, interactionists describe the cause process due to stimulus-response through a graph below (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015).

Figure 1. Stimulus – Response Process in Symbolic Interaction

Furthermore, Griffin added that Blumer's symbolic interaction theory emphasized the importance of language roles in negotiating a meaning or representation. Symbols are likened to a stimulus to someone where this symbol has meaning and value for society. The symbol contains a message that encourages someone to feel and respond to individuals, objects or other objects that are intended (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015). Therefore, the thinking process defined by Blumer is a process of interpretation or meaning of a person depending on his own thought process. This argues derived from Mead's thinking that humans are naturally accustomed to talking to themselves in interpreting situations that are considered difficult. In this case, the human thinking process plays an important role in reading and responding to the meaning of symbols in a social environment (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015).

Mead's concept about *Meaning, Language and Thinking* construct a psychological term related to self-identity. Mead believes that a person will not have a "self identity" without any kinds of interaction process and the exchange of meaning through communication process (Griffin,

Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015). The self-identity or self-concept derives from internal self cognitive that individual basically are taking the role of other. This taking role of other adopted by human through the way how self views another individual and contrariwise in order to shape the interaction process and symbol's meaning exchanges. This self-picture, according to self-looking glass self into two terms, those are "I" and "Me". Potrait "I" refers to the condition of right brain dominant that encourages someone to think themselves imaginatively. The identity of "Me", furthermore, was described as a form of perception of individual as an object, where individual views themselves according to the views of others (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015). In addition, Mead also believes that social society plays a major influence in individual self identity development. Mead describes it as "Generalized Other" that defined as a set of information processed in individual cognition related to certain viewpoints, expectations or attitudes towards another person. This set of information can not constructed alone but influenced by society's norms collectively. This "Generalized Other" behavior triggers intimidator to create labelling or naming towards someone (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015).

2.2 The Shift of People Interaction on Social Networking Site (SNSs)

The symbol's meaning exchange in the process of interaction among individual, before industrial revolution era, is carried out conventionally trough face-to-face communication. According to Goffman, an individual will depend on two basic forms of communication: verbal communication form which is manifested through signs or expressions and non-verbal communication (Canfield, 2002). Changes in the interaction model among individuals was influenced by Computer Mediated Communication (CMC) technology. According to Walther, this CMC encourages Communicator to convey information and to build self-impression through text-based (Walther, 1996). Walther added that CMC is capable to send messages to many recipients without worrying the geographical borders and to coordinate many people into virtual group (Walther, 1996). This concept is the stimulus that forms the phenomenon of virtual communities that connected to each other without the limitations of distance and time.

The presence of Social Network Site (SNSs) and Web 2.0 on the 20th century encourages interpersonal interaction among individuals to a larger scale (Mustafa and Hamzah, 2011). This communication technology assist internet users to communicate each others with high interactivity, inclusiveness, and collaboration(Mustafa and Hamzah, 2011). The presence of this communication technology provides strong influence in changing the human interaction patterns includes the sender, receiver, channel and feedback (Vitak, 2008). Goffman believes that the representation of sender's self-identity is formed and designed in many kinds of visual appearance to achieve a certain level of impression on viewer's perception (Walther, 1996). This is reflected through the characteristics of social media networks based on images rather than text, which is able to produce more interpretation of the physical appearance on self-picture on Social Media. The goal is to strength people's perception toward self that is reflected through the comments addressed to the object or picture (Rassi, 2016).

Similar to the concept of Symbolic Interaction in the real world, text or language becomes the main key in negotiating a meaning of symbol or interpreting existing object in virtual world (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015). Becker added, visual text contains an ideological element in which someone circulates their image equipped with the narratives they write (Davies, 2017). The visual text or captions attached to the self-picture written in social media is able to explain the "self-looking glass" identity of the user. The viewers or followers is capable to assess the

personal identity of the account owner (Jones, 2016). This interpretation then trigger a response that is constructed through non-verbal communication includes text (comments), and emoticons (virtual emotion). Virtual emotion, as a conversion form of gesture and human emotion, plays an important role in affirming emotion contained in social media text (Yuasa, Saito and Mukawa, 2006). This virtual emotion is visualized through the form graphic symbols that present expressions of happiness, sadness, anger, pain, etc.(Chairunnisa and Simangunsong, 2017)

2.3 Cyberbullying in Interpersonal Communication

Before the invention of internet technology, bullying is defined as a form of aggression behavior conducted by intimidator against individual who is considered weak and carried out repeatedly by someone who has power (Bauman and Yoon, 2014). Specifically, Benitez and Justicia classified bullying into two forms: (1) direct bullying through physical interaction like kicking, hitting, threatening with weapons or being done verbally (insulting, blackmailing and others), (2) inderect physical bullying like hiding objects of others, damaging inventory, stealing and others. While verbal form, indirect bullying behavior includes mocking, spreading rumors, etc. (Benítez and Justicia, 2006). The presence of social media networks have changed the pattern of face to face bullying behavior. Compared to traditional bullying, the actor of this cyberbullying are able to disguise their identity so that the attacks to be anonymous and were carried out aggressively (Donegan, 2012). Cyberbullying can be found in the form of any messages or comments for example: lying, mocking, making rude or malicious comments, spreading gossip, making threatening comments through internet communication (e-mail, chat rooms, instant messaging, blogs, sms, website or sent through mobile phone) (David-Fredon and Hertz, 2009). Previous reports related to cyberbullying describes many factors why individual being bullied in social media. Usually it happened to individual with specific identity for instance specific gender, sex orientation, ethnicity, language, nationality, religion or it refers to person with disabilities (British Institute of Human Rights, 2012; Pozza *et al.*, 2016).

Similar to face-to-face bullying takes place in real life, the cyberbullying on social media will involve at least two people in which someone acts as an intimidator and someone else to be a victim (Donegan, 2012). This interpersonal interaction between intimidator and victim is classified as model of interpersonal communication. The previous research has shown that the interaction between intimidator and victim produced various message design logic. Through research of cyberbullying phenomenon on Facebook content in Indonesia, Akbar and Utari concluded three kinds of interchanged message models based on O’Keefe’s theory of message design logic. The research described three types of message design logic used by intimidator: (1) expressive message design logic for instance the use of capital letters in order to insult or to mock victim, the use of emoticons, and specific image to support statements, (2) conventional message design logic was described by intimidator’s suggestion toward victim in accordance with the social norms adopted, and (3) rhetorical message design logic was described by intimidator through negotiated message towards victim that are flexible, insightful and centered on individuals. In general, the rhetorical messages design logic written in form of long comments without any conclusions (Alam and Utari, 2015).

3. Research Context & Data Collection

The context of this study is a man named Ahmad Jaelani. In the virtual world, Jaelani is well-known as a celebrity instagram named Mimi Peri Rapunchelle. His instagram account @mimi.peri was followed by more than 1.4 million followers and has uploaded more than 2.000 personal photos and videos. The existence of Mimi Peri Rapunchelle has attracted a lot of local

and national media. Since 2018, Mimi Peri has covered by more than a dozen of online, printing and national television media. In addition, Mimi Peri has released Youtube channel that published 22 short movies with total 800,000 viewers per episode.

The presence of Mimi Peri Rapunchelle in Instagram was considered as controversial and viral figure among Instagram users in Indonesia. Major followers were interesting in the way he used clothes, make up and performed. The pictures and videos were viral since he used various attributes and symbols on spesific gender. Most of his appearance as seen in Mimi Peri self-picture on Instagram account was similar with woman dressing style. Furthermore, manipulated self-pictures uploaded on Instagram trigger his followers being likes and dislikes. The dislike comments described a disagreement towards personal caption and manipulated woman symbols /attributes conducted by Ahmad Jaelani (Mimi Peri Rapunchelle). All dislike comments written through utterances of degrading, insulting, threatening, or described through emoticon of anger, laughter expression, etc.

In order to describe the main conclusion of data analysis, this study use qualitative-descriptive approach. The primary data such as personal pictures, caption, follower comments and various emoticons contained mocking, insulting, degrading, and threatening are taken and captured randomly. The secondary data of video profile published by media online www.asumsi.com is used in order to describe the self-looking glass of Mimi Peri Rapunchelle. In general, there are 10 personal photos were taken as analytical data. They present symbol of certain genders that is manipulated both conventionally and through the help of photo editor technology.

4. Analysis and Finding

According to the symbolic interaction theoritical framework, the process of interaction among individuals started from the stimulous that derives from individual cognition process itself. This stimulus creates kind of self-identity symbols that interpreted by others. Continuously, this exchange of meaning creates human respon that is formed in various human expressions for instance laughing, smiling, anger, etc. Related to the symbolic interacation happened in the Cyberbullying phenomenon, the process of interpersonal interaction between intimidator and victom described as the diagram below:

Figure 2. Cyberbullying in Social Media based on Symbolic Interactionism Perspective

4.1 *Internal Conflict in Victim's Self-Identity*

At the stimulus stage, the process of symbolic interaction takes place within oneself. In this case, the process of meaning for a symbol, self-looking glasses, and the process of taking role of the other occur through impersonal communication. This is reinforced by the opinion of Mead that naturally, a human being will speak to himself in interpreting a difficult condition (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015). In case of Cyberbullying against Mimi Peri Rapunchelle, the process that happened on this stage described by following reasons:

4.1.1 *Contrastive Self Looking Glass Identity between I vs Me*

In case of Cyberbullying against Mimi Peri Rapunchelle, the construction of "I" self-identity is formed imaginatively and creatively. Ahmad Jailani associates itself as a Mimi Peri or Purity Fairy. He describes itself as a pretty woman, with blue eyes, curly hair and white skin. Meanwhile, the construction of self-identity of "Me" as an object describes itself as a man with the real name of Ahmad Jaelani. He realizes that society view him as a transgender. This personal identity conflict between "I" and "Me" is described through script of personal interview that published by www.asumsi.com on July 6, 2018.

Figure 3. Exclusive Personal Interview with Mimi Peri Rapunchelle

<https://www.asumsi.co/video/mimpi-mimi-peri-dari-kahyangan-ke-hollywood-asumsi-mono>

Table 1. Personal Interview Video Script

NO.	SELF LOOKING GLASS	STATEMENT
1	I (Subjek)	<p>"...Mimi kan artinya ibu, peri kan artinya penolong, jadi aku adalah peri penolong, peri penolong (00'35 : 00'39)</p> <p>"....selama ini kan aku ke khayangan-khayangan selalu apa-apa melewati khayangan gitu. Tidur di hotel mewah, tidur di kasur empuk, kaya gitu. (01'44 : 01'50);</p> <p>"..... Jadi untuk menjadi Mimi Peri Rapunchelle itu aku bebas, kita mau ngapain, mau ngakak, mau apa, mau berasa cantik, mau jadi apa mau jadi sesuka aku. Memang benar-benar ada kekuatan dalam tubuh aku. (04'33 : 04'40)</p> <p>"...aku sebagai Peri Mungil atau peri-peri yang lain harus dipromosikan untuk menunjukkan kecantikannya seperti itu." (11'46 : 11'50)</p>
2	Me (Objek)	<p>"...Aku nama aslinya Ahmad Zaelani dari kampung, pelosok kendari, Sulawesi tenggara..." (00'31 : 00'34)</p> <p>"...cuman kalau aku jadi jaelani tu pemalu, goblok gitu kan, kampung..." (04'28 : 04'32)</p> <p>"Bagaimana sih kalau seorang Bencong gitu ya, walaupun kita bisa melakukan ajaran Islam tapi dalam hati kita gak bisa berbohong kalau aku tuh seorang Bencong..." (08'19 : 08'28)</p> <p>"...Sering kerja dipecah karena aku bencong gitu. Karena mungkin fisik aku yang kurang seperti cowok gitu kan," (09'13 : 09'16)</p> <p>"...Lulus sekolah aku kerja, kaya kuli gitu. Padahal aku adalah cowok yang lemah, kaya tulang lunaklah istilahnya.... Pada akhirnya aku stress, aku nih laki-laki tapi punya sifat yang kayak cewek gitu (08'35 : 08'55)"</p>

4.1.2 *Manipulated symbols and attributes as reflected on self-picture of Mimi Peri*

Rapunchelle on Social Media

The process of taking the roles of others, as conceptualized by Blumer, is started with impersonal interpretation towards symbols of others. Then, the process of thinking and observation is carried out by individual and it adopted by individual as taking a role in social community. In case of this study, the manipulated symbols and attributes is described through Instagram homepage of Mimi Peri Rapunchelle below:

Figure 4. Personal Instagram Homepage @mimi.peri
<https://www.instagram.com/mimi.peri/?hl=id>

The self-pictures are published on social media presents wider meaning of a fairy. The identity of fairy is not limited to a beautiful woman who lives in palace, but also develop into various identities such as actress K- Pop and Hollywood, single mother, or being a Mermaid. Furthermore, fairy fashion style is not only defined as the use of flaming wings, but it extends to the use of costumes made from leaves and flowers, household appliances, or recycled materials such as plastic and waste paper .

Figure 5. Self Picture (Courtesy : Insatagram mimi_peri)

The meaning of beauty also described through manipulated personal pictures. The body as an object being manipulated in order to construct follower perception. Description of beauty, is not interpreted through collective interpretation, but it rather modified personally. The beauty mobile photo editor includes skin editor, perfect eyes editor, magic brush or additional features were used in order to strengthen follower's perception of beauty identity. The manipulated object edited by beauty photo editor can be seen as pictures below:

Figure 6. Self Picture Beauty Editor (Courtesy : Insatagram mimi_peri)

4.1.3 *Language: Negotiations of Meaning System among Society*

The self-identity of "I" in which constructed as a pretty woman in various versions can not be described clearly without the role of language. According to Griffin's perspective, language has the power to negotiate a symbol. Language is also a form of human's natural ability to give labels or to name symbols. Human can design naming of objects, actions, and concepts that are still abstract (Griffin, Ledbetter and Sparks, 2015). The language plays an important role in negotiating the meaning of beauty. Various concept of beauty as described by Mimi Peri Rapunchelle is negotiated and interpreted personally. This negotiated meaning of beauty is described through picture captions below:

Figure 7. Self Picture (Courtesy : Insatagram mimi_peri)

Table 2. Caption

NO.	PICTURE	CAPTION
1	Figure 7	AK WANTAA MANJHAAAAA...SYEDAAAANG DUDUK MENATAP PARA PERJAKAAAA DI BUMI LEEWAT BERANDAAAH. JANGAN BILANG AK SYAHRINI YAAA...AK SYARINANDE. TAG PERJAACA. YG INGIN AK TURUNIN
2	Figure 7	YG KALIAN SUKA DARI GAUN AK APA...MAHKOTA

The caption as described on personal pictures above is negotiated freely. A striking fashion style is used by Mimi Peri Rapunchelle described as pretty dresses. According to Mimi Peri Rapunchelle's perspective, the meaning of pretty dresses were not limited to silk dress but also refer to dress is made of leaves and flowers.

4.2 Society Collective Interpretation towards Victim's Visual Identity

Meaning is the matter part that plays important role in theory of Symbolic Interaction. Blumer believes that a person acts to others based on the signified meaning on individual symbol. Furthermore, meaning is agreed and interpreted collectively by society. It means that the interpreted meaning is alligned with social values that exist in society. It is called as a collective meaning. In this case, followers or virtual society reflects the social values adopted, including traditional customs, culture, and religious values. In case of Cyberbullying on social media, followers associate Mimi Peri Rapunchelle as part of LGBT (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender). Similar to social values on real world, transgender identity is considered as a form of sexual identity deviations that are not included in the Indonesian cultural starch model (Yuliani, 2010). Previous research related to transgender studies have concluded that most of Indonesian social communities do not recognize existence of transgender in their social caste. Transgender is constructed as someone who behaves feministly and has sexual preference with same sex. This stereotypes encourages society to isolate the existence of transgender community (Yuliani, 2010). All symbols and attributes are used by transgenders, most people construct their identity as bland man, "sick", abnormal, disruptive of public courtesy and to be labelled as commercial sex workers (Pradipta Yudah, 2013). According to religious perspective, the public views that transgender is a factor of unrest in society, full of immorality, have no religious values, and being cursed by people because they have same sex sexual orientation (Rahayu, 2017). This transgender symbol then stimulates followers to interpret in various meaning as reflected in the picture comment column.

4.3 Visual Society Response towards Victim Existence in Social Media reflected by Visual Text and Emoticon

The final process of symbolic interactionism is reflected through human response. Before this human response happened, it started from the stage of interpretation towards symbol that happened among individuals. In case of Cyberbullying on social media, the essential meaning of beauty is carried out collectively based on the social experiences and cultural values. The existence of self-identity "I" as an imaginative object triggers constrastive that represented through certain forms of message response. These responses are reflected through utterances of degrading, insulting or threatening on coments coloumn. According to Jones, the social media provides a virtual space that encourages exchange of judgement toward object through form of replies, comments, likes, and posting easier (Jones, 2016). Specifically, the final form of the Cyberbullying process on Instagram are classified based on the message design logic such as expressive, conventional and rhetorical message. Expressive message is illustrated through comments with the use of capital letters or certain emoticons as represent of anger, resentment or demeaning. This is described through the following personal posting:

Table 4. Rhetorical Message Design Logic Comments

NO.	PICTURE	CAPTION	COMMENTS
1	Figure 9	<p>Ak cuma mampu bersolek untuk menangkis bulian</p> <p>KALIAN BULI AK KRNA AK GK SUKSES .KLO AK GK DI TPU ORANG PASTI SUKSES KO .SKRNG AK CUMA BSA DIAM SABAR .DAN AK GK PERNAH MERUGIKAN KALIAN .SUKSES ITU BUAT AK GK MERUGIKAN ORANG LAIN</p>	<p>@hotgas666 emoga lu sadar dan taubat ya bro @mimi.peri , jgn melawan kodrat laki gausah aneh2, itu muka tambah ngeni didandanin, org ngejudge bukan tarpa alasan, namanya saling mengingatkan dan menegur bahwa hal2 unfaedah yg lu lakukan itu secara ga langsung dicontoh sama anak2 ingusan yg mencari jati diri, gawat kankalo bocah2 skrg jadi pen semua, behentilah bersikap seolah lu yang terdzalimi, kalo ga ditegur lu ga akan sadar2 dan makin meresahkan . Segeralah sadar dari dunia khayalan dan ilusi yang lu buat sendiri !!!</p>
2	Figure 9	<p>Menanti pangeran berkuda ku ditengah terik mertari .ak ingin menunjukan pada para lelaki ido ak syanytik ...baju baru ku untuk menonton asian games</p> <p>Mudah mudahan ak bisa menutupi aib tenndah lu ...ak belum bisa ngomong ak hamil apa gk soal nya pamaali kalo pun ak hamil juga bakal keliatan nanti nya ...maf yaaa Minat order dm aja</p>	<p>@indahfajriyah27 Astagfirullah, la haula w alaa quwwata illa billah, cari tenar, cari duit ga usah ampe segiturnya 😊 setiap apa yang kamu lakukan di dunia pasti mempunyai tanggungan kelak di akhirat. Berdirilah dengan kodrat yang telah ditetapkan sebagai seorang laki2. Kamu tuh ganteng tanpa perlu merubahnya menjadi cantik 😊</p>

Figure 10. Conventional Message Comments

Table 5. Conventional Message Design Logic

NO.	PICTURE	CAPTION	COMMENTS
1	Figure 10	<p>MERAH... adalah simbol keberanian ..</p> <p>PUTIH... adalah sybol kesucian</p> <p>Dua warna PUSAKA BANGSA IDIDID</p> <p>DUA wama berbeda dalam satu jiwa .yg mengalir di darahku ..</p> <p>INDONESIA .. berani menantang sbuah perubahan Besar dari Perjajah ..</p> <p>MERDEKAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA IDIDID</p> <p>DIRGAHAYU REPUBLIK INDONESIA KE 73...</p>	<p>@northan.abran33A da baikrya anda segera bertaubat. Untuk terkenal masih baryk cara yg lain kok daripada menyalahi kodrat yg telah ditentukan oleh Allah. Allah senantiasa menyayangi hambanya yg ingin berubah dan bertaubat.</p>
2	Figure 10	<p>Ritual pendem weteng adalah ritual para peri ketika hamil ..sehani sblum melahir kan...ritual ini berfungsi agar apa yg kita ingin kan terlaksana sperti meminta agar jenis kelamin yg di minta jelas dan tdk terjadi kelainan sex sual....ke 17 janin ak yg barada dlm perut harus di timbun dngn kain sutra kayangan agar anak anak ak kelak jika besar menjadi anak anak peri yg berbakti kepada KAY ANGAN...kami bangsa peri slalu berbati hati dlm melakukan suatu hal yg saklar..skalipun bayi yg ak kandung adalah BAYI YG DI BUAHI SECARA ONLINE...</p>	<p>@aang_nhb Mimi karena di buahi secara online, cek terus jaringannya mi, ati2 anak nya nanti korup ga bisa di buka, 🤔🤔 jgn lupa pakai VPN mi biar ga kenak 'Internet Positif' anak nya, semoga lancar sampai pendownloadan eh salah persalinan 🙏🙏</p>

5. Conclusion

The process of Cyberbullying, according to Symbolic Interaction theory, is described as a systematic stages that can not be separated. As Blumer's premise is about mind, self, and

society, the process of bullying in cyberspace against victims is begin from stimulus that is processed in self internal cognition. In case of Cyberbullying against transgender, conflict of self-identity between "I" and "Me" triggers an inconsistency of behavior which is reflected through symbol manipulation. In case of Mimi Peri Rapunchelle, self identity conflict of "I" and "Me" are clearly seen in the self-portrait that published on instagram account. Symbol manipulation is not only limited to the use of certain gender attributes or accessories, but also to manipulate some body parts by using beauty photo editor. It aims to narrow the gap of beauty and its physical appearance. The meaning of beauty also expands broader as the result of language using. Therefore the meaning of beauty, as reflected on Mimi Peri Rapunchelle self-picture, being negotiated and described contrastively.

The unachievable negotiation process towards existence of Mimi Peri Rapunchelle and his label as transgender triggered a response that was actualized through negative comments such as insulting, humiliating and saying harshly. The forms of negative comments can be classified into several forms of message design logic. It dominated by aggressive rather than conventional and rethorical message design logic.

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